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The Role of Classroom Technology in Enhancing Students' Academic Achievement

Christine M. Calinawan*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study determined the impact of the use of classroom technology among teachers to the academic performance of pupils in Select Elementary School for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study answered the following: 1.) the profile of participants in terms of frequency use of these classroom technology: Computer and Projector. 2.) the academic performance of pupils in terms of general average grades in the 2nd grading period. 3.) the relationship between the use of classroom technology and the academic performance of the participants. This study used a descriptive survey research design. The researcher examined the phenomenon through observations and through statistical analysis. Along with questionnaires that was given out to respondents, interview with the respondents and a few experts in this field were also conducted. The respondents of this study were the forty pupils enrolled in the school year 2023-2024. It was randomly selected from 169 learners in every grade level and their academic performance during the 2nd quarter period with the used of classroom technology of teachers. The data revealed that in terms of using computer, there were twenty eight (28) or seventy eight percent (78%) of the respondents answered that their teachers used computer most of the time. This indicated that the teachers of this respondents were most likely used the computer as part of their teaching. In contrast, nine (9) or twenty-five point five percent (22.5%) of the respondents answered that their teachers always use computers. Furthermore, three (3) or seven point five percent (7.5%) Seldom had used computers and no respondents answered on category of never. This study disclosed that the use of computer and projector greatly affected their academic performance. The classroom technologies used by teachers like; Computer and Projector greatly affect the Academic Performance of the pupils. Majority of the respondents obtained a Very Satisfactory grade, and only few obtained Outstanding, however, none got below 80% academic grade. Based on the findings, there was a significant relationship between the academic performance and the used of classroom technology such as computer and projector. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

Keywords: *academic performance, classroom technology*

Introduction

The emergence of technology has made the world into a global village and has transformed teaching and learning processes. Technology integration into classroom instruction has gained much ground in both developed and developing countries. Worldwide research has shown that Information and Communication Technology can lead to improve student learning and better teaching methods.

Furthermore the Philippines was implementing a 12-year basic education (K to 12 curriculum) system with six years of elementary education and four years of junior high school and two years in senior high education. In the new K to 12 curriculum by the Department of Education, there is a mandatory Kindergarten starting school year 2011-2012. With the advent of k to 12 curriculum, the government desires to enhance the academic and technical competence of the pupils and students while in school. One of its very salient provisions is the use of information and communication technology in enhancing teaching and learning. It is projected that the use of technology in the classroom can help the teachers and learners compete globally. Once the teacher and the learner complete literate level in technological advancement and innovation, they are expectedly capable of effectively translating the lesson into performance.

Subsequently it was reported that Philippines is rated at the bottom among countries in Asia in terms of technological enhancement. It is greatly attributed to the declining standards of the Department of Education in delivering quality education. It is the reason why the Department of Education is launching the DepEd Internet Connectivity Project (DICP) in line with the Presidential Directives (Enclosure No. 1) provide the Public Secondary Schools an internet access (DepEd Order n.50, s.2009). Worldwide research that the use of Information and Communication Technology among teachers is very important to improve student learning and better teaching methods. A report made by the National Institute of Multimedia Education in Japan proved that an increase in student exposure to educational ICT through curriculum integration has significant and positive impact on student achievement, especially in terms of "Knowledge- Comprehension" " Practical skill" and "Presentation skill" in subject areas such as mathematics, science, and social study (<http://www.elmglobal.com>,2012).

As time moves on, and technology becomes more engrained in the lives of students, a teacher may consider the benefits of using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the classroom. Technology has become more widely used by students to communicate and the potential of using ICT in the classroom could help to solve the communication problems in education. If teachers can learn to apply ICT in the classroom, students may remember important details that could help to improve learning outcomes. A shift in the role of a teacher utilizing ICTs to that of a facilitator who does not obviate the need for teachers to serve as leaders in the classroom; traditional teacher's leadership skills and practices are still important (especially those related to lesson planning, preparation and follow-up).

Thus, this present study concerned about relationship between the use of classroom technology and how they affect the academic performance of the pupils. With this, the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to the Select Elementary School teachers with their pupils randomly selected on the effects in the use of classroom technology to the academic performance of their pupils.

Research Questions

This study determined the impact of the use of classroom technology among teachers to the academic performance of pupils in Select Elementary School. Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of participants in terms of frequency use of this classroom technology:
 - 1.1. Computer
 - 1.2. Projector
2. What is the academic performance of pupils in terms of general average grades in the 2nd grading period?
 - 2.1. Outstanding
 - 2.2. Very Satisfactory
 - 2.3. Satisfactory
 - 2.4. Fairly Satisfactory
 - 2.5. Did Not Meet Expectation
3. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of pupils and the use of Classroom technology of their teachers when grouped according to the following:
 - 3.1. Computer
 - 3.2. Projector

Literature Review

Student teachers were found to have strong adherence to use of Information and Communication Technology in teaching. This analysis elucidated teacher educators' access to ICT, their intensity of use, their training skills, and their confidence in using ICT. Results showed students' academic performance generally improved with increased teachers' training skills. The intensive use of ICT as a tool in teaching had posed a significant impact on the students' learning. It was therefore recommended for teacher educators to sustain the use of ICT as an effective strategy and continue to access the skills-based approach in the integration of ICT in education (Gomez, 2012).

ICT can improve the quality of education and heighten teaching efficiency through pre-service training and programs that are relevant and responsive to the needs of the education system. This will allow teachers to have sufficient subject knowledge, a repertoire of teaching methodologies, and strategies, professional development for lifelong learning. These programs will expose them to new modern channels of information, and will develop self-guided learning materials, placing more focus on leaning rather than teaching. However, it is important to point out that ICT is used to enhance teaching styles, and should not replace the role of the teacher (Bonifacio, 2013).

Many countries have tried, through various technology interventions, to provide technology-rich learning environments by equipping the schools with the latest technology. The technology interventions come in various forms, including IWBs, one-to-one laptop computing, and computer laboratories, among others. In recent years, the use of technology to enhance teaching and learning processes had increased tremendously, even in developing countries. However, the effective usage of technology interventions is highly dependent on several factors such as teachers' attitude, beliefs, and perceptions; school adoption rate; pedagogical aspects; students' perception and acceptance; and sustainability (Berry, 2011; Gurevich & Gorev, 2012; Lai, 2010; Levin & Wadmany, 2008).

According to the finding of the study about the "Insight into Innovation Classroom Practices with ICT : Identifying the Impetus for Changes", the impact of the ICT has made a positive impact on the changing the modes of teaching and learning in classroom practices from teacher-centered approach to one that is student-centered, irrespective of the region, school level, and type of school. (Wong, Li, Choi, Lee, 2008)

On the other side, ICT integration in daily class practices is significantly associated with the teacher's perspective. Teachers' perspective about the ICT school policy seem to be more important for the ICT integration in the classroom than the teachers' ICT profile (Keer et al., 2012)

There are 13 reasons to use educational technology in lessons, according to Freeman (2011): a) Where information and communication technology (ICT) is taught well, it has been shown to enhance pupils' levels of understanding and attainment on other subjects. This is because "real" ICT is more about thinking skills than about mastering particular software application; b) ICT can provided both the resources and the pedagogical framework for enabling pupils to become effective independent learners.

For the personal-professional tool for teachers, ICT provides a wide range of aids to the personal-professional work of teachers. Here are some common examples. Lesson plans and students hand-outs are stored as word processor files. They are easily modified and brought up to date. Electronics grade book that includes provisions for seating charts, pictures of students, auto matic emailing of

reports to students, and so on. Test generation software, including databanks of exam questions. Access to lesson plans created by others via the Web Access to professional development and training via Distance learning, communication with students and parents. Many teachers have personal Website and/or Websites specifically designed for courses they are teaching. Some teachers develop newsletters that their students take home and communication with one's fellow educators, including sharing of lesson plans and other instructional materials (Moursund, 2006).

A student's academic achievements are often used to evaluate teaching effectiveness and are influenced by the technology in the school. In other words, a student's use of technology represents the teacher's integration of technology into teaching and curricula and also affect teacher's integration of technology into teaching and curricula and also affects teacher's effectiveness (Chang & Wu, 2012).

Methodology

Participants

The participants of this study were the forty (40) pupils of Ulab Elementary School, SY 2023-2024, it was randomly selected from 169 learners in every grade level and their academic performance during the 2nd quarter period with the used of classroom technology of their teachers when grouped according to the following :Computer and Projector. The pupil-respondents were selected through stratified random selection based on the School Form 2 (SF2) Daily Attendance of Learners.

Instrument

The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire adapted from Amorte's dissertation (2013) entitled , “ The Effects of Using Modern Gadgets in Academic Performance of CFCAIans’’. The researcher made a slight modification in the questionnaire.

There were two sources of data in this study. To find out the academic performance of pupil-respondents, the average of Second Quarter grades were acquired. Second source of data was the questionnaire to achieve the purpose of the study. The questionnaire was one of the most common instruments for data gathering. It were intended to obtain information about the condition or practices which respondents to have knowledge.

Procedure

The researcher administered the questionnaire personally to make sure that proper procedure will be followed. However, before the researcher officially distributed the questionnaire and administered the test, a letter was sent to seek permission from the school principal of Ulab Elementary School, Division of Misamis Oriental .The administration and data- gathering was done. Moreover, the pupils' academic performance were collected from their teachers. Scoring Guidelines for the academic performance of the respondents.

The level of proficiency was based on DepEd Order No. 73, S.201 filed entitled “Guidelines on the Assessment and Rating of Learning outcomes under the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum”.

Ethical Considerations

Research ethics must be followed to the letter. Fundamentally, this supported principles vital to cooperative work, including trust, accountability, mutual respect, and fairness, and helped define the real goals of the study, which included knowledge, truth, and error avoidance. This study adhered to and respected the Belmont Report's research ethics guidelines in order to assure ethical research (2010). A person's autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence, justice, informed consent, integrity, confidentiality and data protection, and conflict of interest are all respected under these principles. The researchers also assured the participants that their identity and the data gathered be kept confidential. For data analysis purposes, the teachers' names were replaced with code or set of numbers to ensure that their identity and integrity are kept confidential

Results and Discussion

This part presents the results and findings as well as the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered/arranged according to the specific problems of the study.

This study determined the impact of the used of classroom technology among teachers to the academic performance of pupils in Ulab Elementary School for the school year 2023-2024.

For purposes of clarity and organization, this part presented data in table followed by its appropriate description following the order which the statement of the problems were cited in chapter

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of frequency used of this classroom technology, namely, Computer and Projector?
2. What is the academic performance of pupils in terms of general average grades in the 2nd grading period namely; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory and Did Not Meet Expectation? This chapter discusses the themes from the data analysed. The 20 conversational partners of the study spontaneously shared their experiences and described their stories. The narratives were analyzed and categorized into themes and core ideas.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution in the Use of Classroom Technology*

Technology	Always		Most		Seldom		Never		Total	%
	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P		
Computer	9	22.5%	28	70%	3	7.5%	0	0%	40	100%
Projector	3	7.5%	20	50%	17	42.5%	0	0%	40	100%

As shown on the table above, out of forty (40) pupil-respondents said that Most of the time their teachers used the computer in delivering the lesson with the frequency of twenty-eight (28) or 70%. There were nine (9) or twenty-two point five percent (22.5%) on incurred an answer of Always while three (3) or seven point five percent (7.5%) answered Seldom and nobody casted on the Never category.

On the other hand, in the use of projector, twenty (20) or fifty percent (50%) of the respondents stated that Most of the time their teachers used projector for teaching them in different subjects. However, there were seventeen (17) or forty-two point five percent (42.5%) among respondents said Seldom and there were three (3) or seven point five percent (7.5%) said Always and none in never category.

Obviously, the most impressive used of classroom technology of the pupil-respondents was the computer.

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of pupils' academic performance.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Academic Performance of pupils*

Academic Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	9	22.5%
Very Satisfactory	23	57.5%
Satisfactory	8	20%
Fairly Satisfactory	0	0%
Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0%
Total	40	100%

The table shows that out of 40 pupil-respondents, twenty-three (23) or fifty-seven point five percent (57.5%) rated very satisfactory in their academic performance with a grade point ranging from 85 – 89%; nine (9) or twenty-two point five percent (22.5%) received an outstanding grade with a grade point ranging from 90 – 100%, eight (8) or twenty percent (20%) got a Satisfactory grade with a grade point ranging from 80 – 84% and no one got a grade below 80%.

Apparently, majority of the respondents got Very Satisfactory grades which means that the respondents have a great impact on the classroom technology.

Table 3. *Distribution on the Relationship between the Respondents' Academic Performance and the use of Classroom technology of their teachers*

Use of classroom technology	Correlation on academic performance (r)	Tabular value	Interpretation on correlation	Decision on H_0
Computer	.42	.361	Moderate correlation	Rejected
Projector	.36	.312	Low or slight relationship	Rejected

The computed value which was .42 for the use of computer indicated a correlation, indeed, it was greater than tabular value (.361) which denoted a moderate correlation. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. It implied that there was significant relationship between the Academic Performance and the use of computer.

While the computed value which was .36 for the use of projector indicated a correlation. The result was greater than the tabular value of .312 which signified a low or slight relationship. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. The table disclosed that there was significant relationship between the used of projector and academic performance. Therefore, regardless of moderate correlation or low relationship of the computed value, still it affected the Academic Performance of the respondents.

Conclusions

This study disclosed that the use of computer and projector greatly affected their academic performance. The classroom technologies used by teachers like; Computer and Projector greatly affect the Academic Performance of the pupils. Majority of the respondents obtained a Very Satisfactory grade, and only few obtained Outstanding, however, none got below 80% academic grade. Based on the findings, there was a significant relationship between the academic performance and the used of classroom technology such as computer and projector. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

The following recommendations were given based on the summary of findings and conclusions drawn from the study. The School administrators and teachers may strongly impose on the rules and policies that would adhere on the use of classroom technology and the school principal should take the leadership in establishing linkages with the stakeholders to acquire the needed resources for the

effective implementation of classroom technology integration. Lastly create a planning Team among teachers handling so that they can share each other some resources for instruction. There must be a policy in the use of classroom technology so that students would appreciate its significance and for the future researchers to conduct a parallel study using more variables, wider scope of respondents and research locale.

Insights

The use of technology in the classroom has changed rapidly in the teaching process among teachers. This change has given among teachers to adapt and embrace technology in their classroom instruction. This enables the government to enhance basic education among schools and educators by integrating innovation in their teaching with the use of information and communication technology in enhancing teaching and learning. It is anticipated that with this innovation will have a significance difference in enhancing teaching among teachers.

This is my basis in selecting my study entitled “ Classroom Technology and Academic Performance of Pupils in Ulab Elementary School” out of my curiosity to know effectiveness of classroom technology in hinterland as we always notice that the children in this place are less exposed in terms of technology compared to the urban children.

Through this study it help the government to evaluate the effectiveness of their program like DepEd Computerization Program had the big impact in every learners in our community. It give idea that more program can be implement related to the technology.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Christine M. Calinawan
Matangad Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines